

Digital Addiction and Mental Health in Older Adults:
A Meta-Analysis of Correlations with Depression and Sleep Quality

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Abstract

Introduction: Smartphone and internet use among older adults has expanded rapidly, reshaping communication, social engagement, and access to health-related information [1]. While digital technologies may reduce social isolation and improve connectivity, increasing evidence suggests that problematic or addictive smartphone use may be associated with adverse mental health and sleep outcomes in this population [2]. Aging is intrinsically linked to physiological changes in sleep architecture, a higher prevalence of insomnia, and increased vulnerability to mood disorders, particularly depression, which may amplify the potential harms of excessive or dysregulated digital engagement [3,4]. Although observational studies [5-9] have reported associations between smartphone addiction, impaired sleep quality, and depressive symptoms in older adults, findings remain heterogeneous, and a quantitative synthesis focusing specifically on this population has been lacking.

Materials and Methods: A systematic review and meta-analysis were conducted in accordance with Cochrane Collaboration guidelines and the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) [10]. PubMed, Embase, and the Cochrane Library were searched from inception to January 2026. Eligible studies were cross-sectional or longitudinal observational studies including adults aged ≥ 60 years that assessed smartphone addiction or problematic smartphone/mobile phone use using validated instruments and reported Pearson correlation coefficients between smartphone addiction and depressive symptoms and/or sleep quality. Sleep quality was assessed using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) across all included studies, while depressive symptoms were measured using validated scales such as the Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS-15 or GDS-30) or the depression subscale of the DASS-21. Random-effects models were applied, with correlation coefficients transformed using Fisher's z and back-transformed for interpretation. Heterogeneity was assessed using Cochran's Q and Higgins' I² statistics. Leave-one-out sensitivity analyses were conducted when substantial heterogeneity was observed. Study quality was evaluated using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale [11], and certainty of evidence was assessed using the GRADE framework [12].

Results: Three [5,6,7] observational studies met the inclusion criteria, comprising 1,023 participants from China, Turkey, and Brazil, with a mean age of 66.2 years. All studies employed cross-sectional designs. The pooled analysis demonstrated a statistically significant, moderate positive correlation between smartphone addiction and poor sleep quality ($r = 0.34$; 95% confidence interval [CI]: 0.06 to 0.57), indicating that higher levels of problematic smartphone use were associated with worse sleep quality among older adults. In contrast, the pooled correlation between smartphone addiction and depressive symptoms was positive but not statistically significant ($r = 0.26$; 95% CI: -0.15 to 0.60). Considerable heterogeneity was observed for both outcomes ($I^2 > 95\%$). Sensitivity analyses suggested that one study exerted a disproportionate influence on pooled estimates and heterogeneity; exclusion of this study attenuated effect sizes and substantially reduced heterogeneity, particularly for the sleep quality outcome. Visual inspection of funnel plots suggested asymmetry, consistent with possible publication bias or small-study effects, although interpretation was limited by the small number of included studies.

Discussion: The findings indicate that smartphone addiction is moderately and significantly associated with impaired sleep quality in older adults, supporting the clinical relevance of problematic digital engagement as a contributor to geriatric sleep disturbances. Proposed mechanisms include excessive nighttime device use, cognitive-emotional hyperarousal, exposure to blue light, and circadian rhythm disruption, which may be particularly consequential in older adults with reduced sleep resilience [7,13]. In contrast, the association between smartphone addiction and depressive symptoms was less consistent and did not reach statistical significance, possibly reflecting methodological heterogeneity, differences in measurement instruments, and the multifactorial nature of late-life depression. Bertocchi et al. (2022) [5] observed that in low-income settings, the importance of smartphones correlated with reduced depressive symptoms, as the device may serve as a bridge for social support rather than a source of addictive behavior. This highlights that technology's impact on geriatric mental health is shaped by social context and the nature of its use. Although problematic digital engagement appears to be a relevant and potentially modifiable risk factor for sleep disturbances in aging populations, current evidence is limited by heterogeneity and a small number of studies [16,17]. Identifying addictive smartphone use as a modifiable factor is important for developing interventions aimed at preserving sleep quality and mental health.

Conclusion: This meta-analysis shows that smartphone addiction is linked to poorer sleep quality in older adults, while its association with depressive symptoms remains unclear. Future studies should use longitudinal designs and standardized, age-appropriate tools to better understand causality and guide interventions promoting healthy digital use and mental well-being.

Key-words: Depression; Meta-Analysis; Older adults; Sleep quality; Smartphone addiction.

Abbreviations: CI, Confidence Interval; DASS-21-D, Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale - 21 items (Depression subscale); GDS, Geriatric Depression Scale; GDS-15, Geriatric Depression

Scale - 15 items; GDS-30, Geriatric Depression Scale - 30 items; GRADE, Grading of Recommendations, Assessment and Development and Evaluations; IAT, Internet Addiction Test; MPAS-SV, Mobile Phone Addiction Scale - Short Version; NOS, Newcastle-Ottawa Scale; PRISMA, Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses; PSQI, Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index; r, Pearson correlation coefficient; SAS, Smartphone Addiction Scale; SAS-SV, Smartphone Addiction Scale-Short Version; SD, Standard Deviation.

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Figures and Tables

Table 1: Characteristics of Studies Included in the Meta-Analysis

Characteristic	Bertocchi (2022)	Tian (2023)	Kara, s (2023)
Country	Brazil	China	Turkey
Study design	Population-based cross-sectional	Cross-sectional	Cross-sectional
Sample size (N)	668	459	392
Mean age (SD)	69.50 (7.47)	63.44 (3.96)	65.62 (0.94)
Female, %	50.1%	56.9%	22.7%
Addiction measure	IAT	MPAS-SV	SAS
Depression measure	DASS-21-D	GDS-15	GDS-30

Abbreviations: DASS-21-D, Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale - 21 items (Depression subscale); GDS-15, Geriatric Depression Scale - 15 items; GDS-30, Geriatric Depression Scale - 30 items; IAT, Internet Addiction Test; MPAS-SV, Mobile Phone Addiction Scale - Short Version; SAS, Smartphone Addiction Scale; SD, Standard Deviation.

* Total sample (N = 668) included smartphone users, basic cell phone users, and non-users. Data for correlation analysis were derived from the smartphone user subset (n = 172).

Figure 1: Forest plot of the included studies. Forest plots for the correlation between smartphone addiction and depressive symptoms in older adults, and for the correlation between smartphone addiction and sleep quality in older adults.

